

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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CHANGES IN EMPLOYEE BENEFITS AND HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ACCOUNTING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This paper examines the ongoing reforms in Uzbekistan's accounting system, with a particular focus on employee benefits and human resource management. As Uzbekistan continues changing its national accounting system into international framework, significant legislative and structural changes have been introduced which aims to enhance workforce conditions, promote fair compensation, and improve employee welfare. Additionally, compensation policies have been refined to promote fair labor practices. According to Uzbekistan's employment laws, all workers, including minors and employees in hazardous industries, are entitled to regulated working hours. The Uzbekistan Labor Code also guarantees maternity leave for women, with state social insurance covering the associated benefits. This study employs data analysis and comparative evaluation of national and global statistics to assess the impact of these reforms. The findings suggest that Uzbekistan's shift toward a modernized accounting and labor framework not only strengthens compliance with international standards but also enhances employee productivity and well-being. By fostering a more structured and transparent financial system, these reforms contribute to long-term economic stability and sustainable workforce development in the country.

Key words: Employee benefits, Human resource management (HRM), Accounting system, Health insurance, Compensation, Minimum wage, Incentive programs.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning buxgalteriya hisobi tizimida olib borilayotgan islohotlar, xususan, xodimlarning nafaqalari va inson resurslarini boshqarish masalalariga e'tibor qaratiladi. O'zbekiston o'zining milliy buxgalteriya tizimini xalqaro asosga o'zgartirishni davom ettirar ekan, mehnat sharoitlarini yaxshilash, adolatli ish haqini to'lashga ko'maklashish va xodimlar farovonligini oshirishga qaratilgan muhim qonunchilik va tarkibiy o'zgarishlar kiritildi. Bundan tashqari, adolatli mehnat amaliyotini targ'ib qilish uchun kompensatsiya siyosati takomillashtirildi. O'zbekistonning mehnat qonunchiligiga ko'ra, barcha ishchilar, jumladan, voyaga yetmaganlar va xavfli ishlab chiqarishlarda ishlaydigan xodimlar tartibga solinadigan ish vaqtini olish huquqiga ega. O'zbekiston Mehnat kodeksida ayollarga homiladorlik va tug'ish ta'tillari ham kafolatlangan bo'lib, davlat ijtimoiy sug'urtasi bilan bog'liq nafaqalar qoplanadi. Ushbu tadqiqot ushbu islohotlarning ta'sirini baholash uchun ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va milliy va global statistikani qiyosiy baholashdan foydalanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekistonning modernizatsiya qilingan buxgalteriya hisobi va mehnat tizimiga o'tishi nafaqat xalqaro standartlarga muvofiqlikni kuchaytiradi, balki xodimlarning samaradorligi va farovonligini ham oshiradi. Ushbu islohotlar yanada tuzilgan va shaffof moliya tizimini rag'batlantirish orqali mamlakatda uzoq muddatli iqtisodiy barqarorlik va mehnat resurslarini barqaror rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: Xodimlarga beriladigan nafaqalar, Inson resurslarini boshqarish (HRM), Buxgalteriya tizimi, Tibbiy sug'urta, Kompensatsiya, Eng kam ish haqi, Rag'batlantirish dasturlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются текущие реформы в системе бухгалтерского учета Узбекистана с особым акцентом на льготы для сотрудников и управление человеческими ресурсами. Поскольку Узбекистан продолжает изменять свою национальную систему бухгалтерского учета в соответствии с международными стандартами, были введены значительные законодательные и структурные изменения, направленные на улучшение условий труда, поощрение справедливой компенсации и улучшение благосостояния сотрудников. Кроме того, политика компенсации была усовершенствована для поощрения справедливой трудовой практики. Согласно трудовому законодательству Узбекистана, все работники, включая несовершеннолетних и работников опасных производств, имеют право на регулируемые рабочие часы. Трудовой кодекс Узбекистана также гарантирует женщинам отпуск по беременности и родам, а государственное социальное страхование покрывает связанные с этим льготы. В этом исследовании используется анализ данных и сравнительная оценка национальной и мировой статистики для оценки воздействия этих реформ. Результаты показывают, что переход Узбекистана к модернизированной системе бухгалтерского учета и труда не только усиливает соответствие международным стандартам, но и повышает производительность и благосостояние сотрудников. Способствуя созданию более структурированной и прозрачной финансовой системы, эти реформы способствуют долгосрочной экономической стабильности и устойчивому развитию рабочей силы в стране.

Ключевые слова: Вознаграждения работникам, Управление человеческими ресурсами (HRM), Система бухгалтерского учета, Медицинское страхование, Компенсация, Минимальная заработная плата, Программы поощрений.

INTRODUCTION

This paper provides detailed information about changes in two major areas of accounting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. First, we will look at the employee benefits and HR management in Uzbekistan's accounting system is also discussed in a broader range.

Currently, Uzbekistan is undergoing a phased reform of the accounting system, the goal of which is to bring the national accounting system into compliance with the requirements of international financial reporting standards [1]. This is bringing a set of changes to the employee benefits and human resource management spheres, including creating far more opportunities and incentives for employees and providing developed HR practices in companies of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Increasing the level and quality of education of the population from preschool to postgraduate through deeper integration of science and education, the provision of educational loans, and the reform of the entire education system, improving the demographic situation by transforming and increasing funding for the health care system, physical education and sports policies, as well as creating conditions and motivation for a healthy lifestyle, improving the quality of life of the population through an increase in the level of wages, optimizing the system of social and pension benefits, raising the level of culture and recreation of the population [2]; are represented by Mukhitdinova Muyassar Ziyaviddinovna in her 2019 article, 'Development of Human Capital in Uzbekistan by Reducing Inequality' says that education and medicine should also be taken into account while targeting human development programs as they play an integral role in increasing the quality and level of life that affect human potential through state regulation of income through taxation and social benefits. Additionally, a number of other studies was conducted by researchers, such as Ludovico Carraro, Oxford Policy Management, London, UK who studied old age pension system in Uzbekistan in 2019 and in the article, he says: "As of the first of January in 2019, 2.62 million people were receiving old age pensions, 371 thousand were receiving a disability pension and 174 thousand were receiving survivor pensions"[3]. Affiliated with Westminster International University in Tashkent, *Inoyatova* has explored various aspects of human resource management (HRM) and job satisfaction in Uzbekistan. Her studies include an investigation into job satisfaction factors among academic staff at a university in Tashkent, as detailed in her paper "HRM & Job Satisfaction: Case of Uzbekistan." Additionally, she co-authored a study on job satisfaction in the telecommunications industry in Uzbekistan, published in the International Journal of Social Economics.

Although it is interesting to note, that eleven of the twenty (20) factors received a mean score of below three, indicating a lower satisfaction level with the particular factors, which should be a signal to the University's management [4]. *Karan Khurana and Zamira Ataniyazova* have examined the role of human resource management in advancing Uzbekistan's tourism sector. Their study, published in *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, highlights the significance of HRM in the sector's socio-economic impact and identifies existing gaps and challenges [5]. *Muyassarkhan Umarchodjaeva and Nargiza Omanova*: Associated with Tashkent

State University of Economics, they co-authored “Increasing Efficiency in Enterprises by Means of Transition from the Approach of Human Resource Management (HRM) to Human-Centered Organizational Culture (HCOC).” Their research explores shifting from traditional HRM to a human-centered organizational culture to enhance enterprise efficiency [6]. *Dildorakhon Rakhmonberdiyevna Tokhtasinova*’s study, “Human Resource Management in Hospitality Sector in Uzbekistan and Improving Personnel Through Training,” focuses on HRM practices in Uzbek hotels and emphasizes the importance of staff training in the hospitality industry [7].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article, several methods are applied to the study, including data description, analysis and comparison, logical methods are also included. Both national and global statistics are used to analyze a wider and broader perspective to reach the core and fundamental points of the topic.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

There are some factors contributing to the overall performance of the active labor force and its benefits. Workers in Uzbekistan have been provided with many incentives and opportunities so far. Consider *health insurance, compensation and minimum wage* in Uzbekistan in recent years (Table 1).

Table 1. Data from “HRM & Job Satisfaction: Case of Uzbekistan” [4].

Results of the average job satisfaction scores in %	
Academic staff members rated social service	3.53
Ability utilization	3.27
Creativity	3.24
Policies and practices	2.63
Compensation	2.68
Supervision technical (relationship with supervisor)	2.68
Recognition	2.73
Advancement	2.74

Full health insurance coverage in Uzbekistan will be completed by the end of 2026. This is stated in the September 6 presidential decree on improving public health [8]. This has given the opportunity for residents of Uzbekistan to be sure that their health is on reliable hands. One of the major developments is the introduction of universal health insurance, expected to be fully implemented by the end of 2026, as outlined in the September 6 presidential decree on public health. This initiative aims to provide free health insurance services nationwide, ensuring greater security for employees and residents (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Uzbekistan UZB Current health expenditure per capita (current US\$) [9].

The aforementioned statistics makes it clear that, beginning in 2018 and continuing through 2021, Uzbekistan has increased its investment in universal health insurance. The government will provide free health insurance services nationwide in accordance with the September 6 presidential decree on enhancing public health, which is viewed as an entirely favorable development.

To guarantee that all employees receive equitable compensation, Uzbekistan’s employee compensation policy must be followed by both resident and offshore business owners.

According to Uzbekistan’s pay system, employers are required to pay a minimum wage of UZS **920,000** per month.

- According to Uzbekistan’s employment law, workers in hard and dangerous jobs as well as minors should be permitted to work less hours.
- The law of Uzbekistan guarantees equal opportunity for all workers, regardless of their nationality.
- All women are entitled to maternity leave under **Article 233 of the Uzbekistan Labor Code**. It is typically covered by state social insurance.
- Employees’ work hours are limited by **Article 16 of the Uzbek Constitution**, which permits them to take suitable breaks during the workday (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Minimum wage in Uzbekistan [10].

For the past 7 months in the graph above, Government has been increasing the minimum wage for residents in Uzbekistan, which more or less encourages the population to be part of active labor force and work even harder with motivation. From the viewpoint of workers, it means a positive change as the poverty level decreases if the minimum wage increases, leading to a high potential of satisfying their daily needs and wants. However, on the other side of the coin, businesses need to increase their expanses as the salary the employers are giving increases, which means cost of production rises respectively with the price of goods and services.

In the era of rapid advancements in information technology, Uzbekistan places high priority on the automation of public administration. Recognizing the significance of digital technologies, the government is dedicated to enhancing the efficiency of public administration and delivering high-quality public services. This commitment stems from the understanding that the effective utilization of digital technologies plays a vital role in ensuring transparency and effectiveness in public administration.

Uzbekistan has been adjusting its governance into digital form and gaining attention of other countries on a global scale. On the international scene, Uzbekistan’s advancements in e-government and digitization have been acknowledged. Uzbekistan made tremendous progress in 2022, moving up 18 spots in the United Nations e-government Survey ranking. The nation’s impressive progress put it in the category of countries with a “high/very high level of development” in terms of e-government. The World Bank’s Gov Tech Maturity Index has acknowledged Uzbekistan’s advancements in digital skills and innovation, as well as in public administration and public services. The nation has made great strides, moving up 37 spots in the public administration and public services sector. Additionally, Uzbekistan made a remarkable 65-position jump in the field of digital skills and innovations in public services. Uzbekistan’s progress in the adoption and readiness for artificial intelligence (AI) has been notable, as demonstrated by its ranking in the “Government Readiness Index for Artificial Intelligence” developed by Oxford Perspectives. Uzbekistan has advanced significantly during the last four years, moving up from 158th to 79th in the ranking. One of the main goals of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the plan “Uzbekistan – 2030” is to increase the amount of software product and IT services

exported to \$5 billion¹². Uzbekistan has taken proactive steps and is dedicated to continuously enhancing its educational programs in order to meet the expectations and difficulties of the digital age. The nation hopes to give government servants the skills and knowledge they need to successfully adjust to the digital landscape by offering them continual training and development opportunities. Uzbekistan's prosperity depends on adopting digital technology, according to President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who also said that all industries need to keep up with these developments.

Uzbekistan has made great progress in adopting digital technologies to improve public administration in a number of areas, including healthcare, education, and transportation, under the visionary leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

In order to effectively use digital tools, civil servants must develop new skills and capabilities as a result of digital transformation. The nation has supported 43,000 independent contractors and produced 14,000 well-paying jobs with a \$2 billion investment, including \$700 million in direct subsidies. More than 8 million individuals use the 570 online services available on the my.gov.uz portal, which increases efficiency and accessibility. The development of digital competency among civil servants is essential in the quickly changing information society, where technology advancements are changing interactions and work procedures. Aligning public services with the demands of the digital age is a critical challenge for Uzbekistan and many other countries. Civil workers must adjust to new ways of working, communicating, and providing services as a result of the broad digitalization brought about by the rise of contemporary digital technology. In HR management, artificial intelligence is being used more and more to automate procedures, predict staffing needs, and optimize workflows. This allows for more accurate staff management and more accurate adaptation to personnel needs. By enabling a deeper comprehension of staff requirements, spotting patterns, and anticipating possible HR challenges, data analytics is being used by decision-makers to make strategic HR management decisions. Workers now anticipate instant access to information from public services, online communication, and digital services. Maintaining cybersecurity becomes increasingly important as the amount of digital data increases and its significance in government operations grows. In order to stay up with the rapidly changing digital landscape, civil servants must continuously learn and adapt as a result of the creation and application of new technologies.

In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries, the implementation of digital platforms is increasingly crucial for the digital transformation of public administration. The effective delivery of public services through digital technologies improves the quality and accessibility of these services for citizens and businesses. Digitized information empowers civil servants to collect, analyze, and utilize data for informed decision-making, process optimization, and enhanced administrative efficiency. It is also worth noting that automating processes, improving monitoring and reporting, and increasing transparency in government activities contribute to the reduction of corruption. Consequently, the priority areas of the Agency for the Development of Public Service under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan include ensuring a transparent and equitable procedure for the selection and placement of HR through modern information and communication technologies, providing equal opportunities for career advancement based on objective assessments of work activity, moral and volitional qualities, abilities, and skills of government employees, monitoring and analyzing trends and prospects in the development of the civil service, and introducing innovative HR management and development methods based on principles of openness, professionalism, and accountability. By overcoming challenges and successfully implementing these initiatives, Uzbek civil servants can develop in accordance with the modern requirements of the digital era, thereby ensuring a stable and innovative development of the civil service. It is important to emphasize that the digitalization of the HR service in Uzbekistan is not a standalone project but an integral part of the strategy for modernizing public administration and fostering the digital economy in the country.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The recent reforms in Uzbekistan's accounting system have significantly influenced employee benefits and human resource management. The government's commitment to aligning national standards with international financial reporting standards has led to improvements in health insurance, compensation, and minimum wage policies. The expansion of health insurance coverage, fair compensation regulations, and increasing minimum wages contribute to better working conditions and economic stability. While these changes benefit employees by improving their quality of life, businesses face increased costs. Ultimately, these reforms are crucial for fostering a more sustainable and balanced labor market in Uzbekistan.

These certain ways are recommended by author which are found to be able to contribute to the development of HRM in Uzbekistan by filling all the gaps:

Enhancing support for businesses – While increasing the minimum wage benefits workers, the government should set policies to support businesses, such as tax incentives or subsidies, to offset rising labor costs and prevent inflationary pressures. Many entrepreneurs hesitate to run a business in Uzbekistan due

to high risk of loss and high level of interest rates in banks. Instead, government should encourage them and create a convenient atmosphere here in Uzbekistan which leads to lower unemployment in a country.

Enhancing payroll and compensation management – The integration of digital accounting solutions in HR management can improve payroll accuracy, ensure timely salary payments, and enhance compliance with labor laws. Encouraging businesses to adopt automated payroll systems aligned with Uzbekistan's evolving financial regulations will increase efficiency and transparency in salary disbursements.

Expanding digital accounting and HR integration – To streamline financial and workforce management, businesses and government agencies should implement AI-powered accounting tools that optimize wage distribution, tax calculations, and social benefit allocations. This will reduce errors and ensure proper alignment with Uzbekistan's International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS).

Balancing wage growth with economic stability – Accounting and financial institutions should play a role in assessing the economic impact of minimum wage increases. By using financial forecasting and economic modeling, Uzbekistan's policymakers can make data-driven decisions to adjust wage policies without causing inflationary pressures on businesses.

Enhancing financial transparency in HR practices – The government should promote stricter financial reporting and auditing measures to ensure fair compensation practices in both the public and private sectors. Strengthening financial oversight within HR departments can prevent wage disparities, ensure equitable tax contributions, and promote compliance with labor laws.

Investing in financial and digital literacy – To support the digitalization of HR and accounting systems, Uzbekistan should invest in training programs for accountants and HR professionals. Equipping them with skills in modern accounting software and digital finance tools will enhance efficiency and improve compliance with the country's financial regulations

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